

closer affinity to the *O. glaberrima*-*O. barthii* group than to the Asian *O. rufipogon* group, although it had been considered a subtype of *O. rufipogon*.

The Asian group comprised four or five loosely knit groups, each corresponding to the indica type (including some *O. rufipogon*), japonica type (including *O. rufipogon* from China), *O. rufipogon* (consisting of several subgroups), and *O. nivara* (see figure). Some *O. rufipogon*-*O. nivara* showed close affinity to cultivated rice, as suggested by previous studies (Wang et al 1992, Nakano et al 1992).

Three accessions of perennial *O. rufipogon* from Papua New Guinea (excluded from the figure) carried both fragments of *O. rufipogon* and *O. meridionalis*. Although no *O. meridionalis* has been reported from Papua New Guinea so far, it is possible that some exist in the country and that the natural hybrids between *O. rufipogon* and *O. meridionalis* could have survived until now.

The classification among species matched well with the findings of previous studies (Morishima 1969, Second 1985, Wang et al 1992). Further analysis is needed to reveal the relationships among Asian subgroups.

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Detection of D genome chromosomes by genomic in situ hybridization

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Based on chromosome pairing at meiosis, it is known that the genus *Oryza* has five genomes (A, B, C, E, and F) in the diploid species. Tetraploid species with BC or CD genomes have also been found, although a diploid species with the D genome has not yet been discovered. The D genome is only found in tetraploids (*O. alta*, *O. grandiglumis*, and *O. latifolia* from Central and South America) in combination with the C genome.

In this study, we visualized D genome chromosomes on a glass slide in a CD genome tetraploid species. We used a chromosome painting method in which we applied the genomic in situ hybridization (GISH) method, using the total genomic DNA isolated from a C genome diploid species, *O. officinalis* (2n=24), labeled with biotin as the probe. *O. latifolia* was used to prepare chromosomes.

Chromosome samples were prepared by an enzymatic macerated/air drying method. The chromosome samples were treated with an enzymatic mixture (2% cellulase onozuka RS, 1.5% macerozyme R-200, 0.3% Pectolyase Y-23), proteinase K (1 mg ml⁻¹), 4.5% acetic acid, and RNase A (1 mg ml⁻¹) prior to in situ hybridization to get clear genome-specific fluorescent signals on small chromosomes.

The post-treatment removed cytoplasmic debris, cellular protein, and RNAs that cause nonspecific signals. In addition, a modified thermal cycler with a flat aluminum plate was developed and used to precisely control temperature. The results of GISH were analyzed using CHIAS 2, an image-analyzing system that provides clear fluorescent signal reproduction. This system can capture the fluorescent signals of GISH within a second, enhance weak signals, and even superimpose the signal images onto the original chromosome

We identified 24 C genome chromosomes, detected by the fluorescent probe of *O. officinalis*, from a mixture of 48 *O. latifolia* chromosomes belonging to the C and D genomes. All 24 D genome chromosomes were clearly identified using the imaging method, as were 24 C genome chromosomes from the 48 chromosomes with B and C genomes.

We also found differences in the relative strength of fluorescent signals between C and D genomes, and between B and C genomes. The differences in the fluorescent signal strength between B and C genome chromosomes were more distinct than those between C and D genome chromosomes, despite applying the same probe. These differences reflect the sequence homology between the C and D or B genomes. The D genome is considered to be more similar to the C genome than to the B genome.

We will continue to use the GISH method to provide new information about the relationships among the six genomes in *Oryza*. ■

Fingerprinting rice germplasm using ALP and PCR-based RFLP

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Morphological and isozyme markers provide a simple method for classifying rice collections. However, the markers available and their level of polymorphism are inconveniently low. DNA markers, on the

other hand, are abundant, high in their level of polymorphism, and known to be useful for germplasm surveys.

We evaluated the usefulness of converting mapped restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP) markers to polymerase chain reaction (PCR)-based markers, such as amplicon length polymorphism (ALP), and PCR-based RFLP (Ghareyazie et al 1995). This is the first report on applying ALP and or PCR to classify rice and on classifying Iranian rice varieties at the DNA level.

We used a set of 35 Iranian varieties, along with three indica and two japonica varieties as references (Fig. 1). A set of 15 pairs of primers were used to amplify genomic DNA isolated from the 40 varieties. To examine ALPs, PCR products were separated in agarose gels containing ethidium bromide. The products were then digested with nine different restriction endonucleases (recognizing 4-5 bases) and separated on either agarose or polyacrylamide gels. Amplified PCR products and patterns generated upon their digestion were scored for the presence or absence of bands in each variety. These data were used to construct a resemblance matrix according to Dice distance coefficients. We used the NTSYS program to perform cluster analysis and to build the dendrogram according to the UPGMA clustering method.

Agarose and or polyacrylamide gel analysis of the digested PCR products showed a variety of banding patterns.

Diversity at loci RG118, RG13, and RG235 was exhibited prior to and/or after digestion of PCR products (Fig. 2). Six of the 15 pairs of primers used showed ALPS (Fig. 2c, e). The others generated monomorphic PCR products across 40 varieties (Fig. 2a). These monomorphic banding patterns were converted to polymorphisms by digesting PCR products with MvaI (Fig. 2b).

$$\text{Using the formula } NP = \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} (X_i \times \sum_{j=i+1}^n X_j)$$

where n is the total number of alleles in a given locus, and X_i and X_j are the number of varieties carrying the i th and j th alleles, respectively, we calculated the number of polymorphic pairs (NP) as a measure of the abundance of ALP (13%) and PCR (28%) in rice.

A dendrogram was built from the genetic distances' matrix (Fig. 1). A clear distinction exists between the two major rice subspecies, indica and japonica. Three groups were distinguished among Iranian

varieties, (indicas and japonicas, and varieties that are genetically distinct from both indica and japonica types). The varieties are traditionally divided into the major groups of Sadri, Champa, and Gerdeh.

One major group included all of the Sadri-type varieties from northern Iran (Guilan and Mazandaran provinces), where rice is the major crop. This group was clustered with two japonica standards. The second group included only six varieties (entries 5, 9, 14, 15, 21, and 16, Fig. 1). It was not clustered with any of the standard varieties, indicating the varieties probably evolved independently within the country.

The third group, the smallest one, included only three Champa varieties from Iranian germplasm and was clustered with the three indica standard varieties.

Sadri-type varieties, which are strongly scented and well known for their cooking quality, are genetically closer to japonicas

1. Dendrogram based on Dice's genetic distances demonstrating relationships among 40 rice varieties. Genetic distance was calculated according to Dice's method based on the pooled ALP and P-BR data of 13 loci. The NTSYS program was used to build the dendrogram according to the UPGMA clustering method.

2. Ethidium bromide staining of PCR products for RG118 (A), RG13 (C) and RG235 (E) loci amplified from total genomic DNA of Iranian varieties and restriction fragments generated from the products digested with *MvaI* (B) and *HinfI* (D). The numbers for each lane are the entry numbers used in Figure 1. The approximate size of bands is shown in the base pair.

than to indicas. Despite their very typical indica morphology (long and cylindrical seed, tall stature, narrow leaves), these varieties, as well as some of the Champa-type varieties, are clustered with standard japonicas. This suggests that the morphological characteristics are not representative of the genetic status of a given variety, and as revealed by Glaszmann (1987), these varieties may belong to isozyme group V

and are therefore neither pure indica nor pure japonica.

We found PCR-based RFLP to be faster, easier, and relatively cheaper than Southern-based RFLP. PCR markers are now abundant, with known map locations. Their application is highly reproducible and more informative than randomly amplified polymorphic DNA.

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Distribution and evolutionary differentiation of mitochondrial plasmidlike DNAs in the genus *Oryza*

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We investigated the distribution of plasmidlike DNAs homologous to those of *O. sativa* in the genus *Oryza* and found some evolutionary differentiations of plasmidlike DNAs. Four kinds of circular mitochondrial plasmid-like DNAs, designated B1, B2, B3, and B4, have been detected in many *Oryza sativa* strains and analyzed in DNA sequences.

We first analyzed the distribution of plasmidlike DNAs homologous to those of *O. sativa* in 40 strains of the genus *Oryza* with AA, BB, BBCC, CC, CCDD, and EE genomes (Miyata et al 1995). Using the B1, B2, B3, and B4 clones as probes, plasmidlike DNAs were observed only in varieties with AA, CC, and CCDD genomes. The distribution patterns of strains with the AA genome were highly polymorphic. This suggests that the disappearance of plasmidlike DNAs occurred during the diversification of strains with the AA genome.

We then amplified the plasmidlike DNAs from strains with the AA genome by polymerase chain reaction (PCR) and examined restriction fragment length polymorphisms (RFLPs). RFLPs were detected among plasmidlike DNAs amplified from different strains (Miyata et al 1995), indicating some mutations, such as base substitutions.

In CC and CCDD genomes, some signals hybridized with the B1 probe showed rather different restriction patterns, indicating that these signals are new plasmidlike DNAs homologous to B1. We cloned them and named them M1, M2, and M3. Their entire nucleotide sequences were determined; M1 is 2,430 bp in size, M2 is 2,034 bp, and M3 is 2,096 bp. We compared each of these sequences and found that M1, M2, and M3 share high homology to B1. B1, M2, and M3 each lack about 300 bp of a region that is present in M1, and small repeats were found at the sites of deleted sequences (see figure).

We therefore propose the hypothesis that the B1 family differentiated from a common ancient molecule that was similar to M1 through slipped mispairing during DNA replication at several stages in the evolution in the genus *Oryza*.